

*Research Lifecycle Management technologies for
Earth Science Communities and Copernicus users in EOSC*

Deliverable D4.2 Data Cube API – Release I

Grant agreement number	101017501
Start date of the project	Reliance
Duration of the project	24 months
Type of Action	Research and Innovation Action
Coordinator	PSNC

Due date of delivery	30/06/2021
Actual date of delivery	08/07/2021
Work package	WP4
Type of deliverable	Report
Dissemination level	Public
Responsible	MEE0
Reviewer	PSNC
Version	1.0

This project has received funding from the European research infrastructures (including e-Infrastructures) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101017501

List of authors, contributors and reviewers

Name	Role	Organization
Simone Mantovani	Author	MEE0
Sergio Ferraresi	Contributor	MEE0
Fabio Govoni	Contributor	MEE0
Mario Cavicchi	Contributor	MEE0
Raul Palma	Reviewer	PSNC

History of changes

Version	Date	Change	Authors	Organization
0.1	30/06/2021	Version ready for revision	Simone Mantovani	MEE0
1.0	08/07/2021	Final version	Simone Mantovani	MEE0

Glossary

Acronym	Explanation
AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure
ADAM	Advanced geospatial Data Management
API	Application Program Interface
CAMS	Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service
DAS	Data Access System
EO	Earth Observation
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reproducible
MEEO	Meteorological and Environmental Earth Observation
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OIDC	OpenID Connect
RELIANCE	Research Lifecycle Management technologies for Earth Science Communities and Copernicus users in EOSC
RO	Research Object
SSO	Single Sign-On
WCS	Web Coverage Service

Table of Contents

1	Executive Summary	6
2	Introduction	6
2.1	<i>Data Cubes</i>	6
2.2	<i>ADAM platform</i>	7
2.2.1	Principles and architecture	7
2.2.1	Authentication and Users Management.....	8
2.2.2	ADAM interfaces	9
3	Application Programming Interface	9
3.1	<i>Data discovery service - OpenSearch</i>	9
3.1.1	Discovery Level 1: datasets discovery.....	10
3.1.2	Discovery Level 2: discovery of products.....	11
3.2	<i>Data access service - WCS</i>	13
3.2.1	GetCapabilities	13
3.2.2	DescribeCoverage	13
3.2.3	GetCoverage.....	14
4	References	16

List of Figures

Figure 1	ADAM Data Access System (DAS) module.....	7
Figure 2	ADAM high-level architecture	8
Figure 3	ADAM Sign-in interface.....	8
Figure 4	Result example of OpenSearch request to list all available datasets in ADAM	10
Figure 5	Result example of OpenSearch request to retrieve details of a datasets in ADAM.....	11
Figure 6	Result example of OpenSearch request to retrieve the list of all products in ADAM.....	12
Figure 7	Result example of OpenSearch request to retrieve all products of a datasets in ADAM	12
Figure 8	Result example of WCS request to retrieve list of datasets (collections) in ADAM	13
Figure 9	Result example of WCS request to retrieve details of a dataset (collection) in ADAM	14
Figure 10	Result example of WCS request to retrieve a product from a dataset in ADAM.....	15
Figure 11	Result example of WCS request to retrieve a product from a dataset in ADAM with MPL_winterInv colortable	16

1 Executive Summary

RELIANCE, short for Research Lifecycle Management for Earth Science Communities and Copernicus users in EOSC, aims to realize the vision of FAIR research in EOSC by adopting a holistic research management approach based on three key and complementary technologies: i) Research objects (RO) as the overarching mechanism to manage scientific research activities; ii) data cubes as the mechanisms enabling an efficient and scalable Earth Observation data discovery and access; iii) text mining and semantic enrichment services allowing to extract machine-readable metadata from RO resources, enabling researchers to discover scientific information at scale and to structure their own research.

This document describes the Data Cube API released to describe and exploit the FAIR Data Cubes made available within the RELIANCE project. The Data Cube Metadata Model adopted for describing FAIR Data Cubes and the list of Data Cube resources are detailed in the [D4.1] and [D4.4], respectively.

A second release of this deliverable is planned at month M18 to track the evolution of Data Cube API: feedback collected within RELIANCE project will be gathered with the Open Geospatial Consortium standardization body to contribute to the definition of specifications for the Data Cube API within the Testbed 17 Innovative Initiative.

2 Introduction

2.1 Data Cubes

The concept of Data Cube applied to geospatial data has progressively gathered more and more consensus as an effective technology to support the uptake of satellite EO applications. In the international scenario, Data Cubes are being progressively adopted at national level to provide a common reference and data access infrastructure for geospatial data, mostly related to the access and exploitation of large collections of multi-temporal, multi-resolution satellite imagery. Data Cube technology is rapidly evolving thanks to the parallel evolution of data storage systems (e.g., the progressive affirmation of object storage in cloud environment), databases and elastic and scalable computing capacities.

Although the definition of Data Cube is still missing, and both users' communities and standardization bodies (e.g., Open Geospatial Consortium) are working on it, Data Cubes are widely considered as a technological enabler providing efficient and cost-effective interfaces to access large volumes (and large variety) of geospatial data (EO and non-EO).

A Data Cube generally is represented as a multi-dimensional data concept (which can be 1-dimensional, 2-dimensional, 3-dimensional, or higher-dimensional), but more in general a Data Cube consists of a comprehensive set of functions:

- to describe the data structure (e.g., its spatial resolution or temporal dimensions and granularity), and more precisely
 - Dataset: a collection of products e.g., grouped by phase mission.
 - Product: a single file which is made available, e.g., through the ADAM Space service
- to describe all the available services to exploit discovery, access, view and analytics services

In the framework of RELIANCE project, the ADAM platform is used as reference implementation of Data Cube: in order to integrate in the European Open Science Cloud infrastructure, the FAIR Data

Cube services and guarantee a high level of interoperability and reusability of Copernicus and non-Copernicus data, the harmonization and alignment with ongoing OGC Testbed17 activities¹ is also pursued.

2.2 ADAM platform

The Advanced geospatial Data Management platform (ADAM) is a tool to access a large variety and volume of global environmental data. ADAM allows you extracting global as well as local data, from the past, current time, as well as short term forecast and long-term projections. Most of the data are updated daily to allow users having always the most recent data to play with.

In the framework of RELIANCE project activities, an ad-hoc instance of ADAM is deployed and configured to access Copernicus and non-Copernicus satellite- and model-based data.

2.2.1 Principles and architecture

The core of ADAM is a Data Access System (DAS), a software module that manages a large variety of geospatial information that feature different data format, geographic / geometric and time resolution. It allows accessing, visualizing, sub-setting, combining, processing, downloading all data sources simultaneously. The DAS exposes OGC Open Search and Web Coverage Service (WCS 2.x) interfaces that allow discovering available datasets and subset them in any dimension with a single query (see figure below).

Figure 1 ADAM Data Access System (DAS) module

ADAM is a very modular platform: various DAS are deployed on different data sources (DIAS Mundi, DIAS creodias, Amazon Web Services - AWS, MEEO Data Facility, SISTEMA Data facility), allowing accessing and sub-setting the available datasets without downloading / duplicating the data. Distributed data sources are made accessible through the Data Cube layer, that exposes OGC-standardised interfaces. On top of the Data Cube layer, platform-based interfaces (web application, mobile application, Jupyter Notebook and APIs) as well as third party user interfaces can be deployed.

¹ <https://www.ogc.org/projects/initiatives/t17>

Figure 2 ADAM high-level architecture

ADAM, referred also as a virtual Data Cube technology, enables seamless access to all available datasets through a single interface to allow developing user-centred solutions on top of it; cutting the access barriers to a large variety of data (no need to know the exact format of any of the available datasets) it saves data preparation time and facilitates the simultaneous use of data coming from different sources.

2.2.1 Authentication and Users Management

The Authentication, Authorization and Accounting (AAA) service is a generic module based on OAuth and OpenID Connect (OIDC) technologies, that allows the integration of customised as well as third-party authentication systems, such as NextGEOS SSO, Google, LinkedIn, and any other OAuth/OIDC provider. It can also be adapted to manage Microsoft Active Directory login. The figure below gives examples of internal (MEE0) and external OIDC providers currently managed by ADAM.

In the framework of RELIANCE project activities, the ROHub OpenID Connect endpoint has been integrated and configured to provide the RELIANCE users a unified Single Sign-On (SSO) entry point to all service components. Furthermore, since ROHub IdAM system is connected to EOSC AAI via the EGI check-in service, it provides ADAM users SSO across all the EOSC services.

Figure 3 ADAM Sign-in interface

2.2.2 ADAM interfaces

ADAM offers the following interfaces for data access

- the **Explorer**, a web-based graphic user interface to allow users to explore, access, process and download data. Explorer includes also and Operator Interface, data processing interface and a mobile application (ADAM Mobile)
- the **Jupyter Notebook**, a web-based processing environment to allow users to import, write and execute code that runs close to the data, exploiting the power and the APIs on a remote computation environment (no user resources are used)
- The **adamapi** python-library to directly access the ADAM data access and processing capabilities directly integrated in the user's code and applications.
- The **Application Programming Interface (API)**, that provide machine-to-machine interfaces for data discovery and data access services.

This document focuses on the Application Programming Interface (API). Explorer, Jupyter Notebook and adamapi will be described in the second release of the Data Cube API deliverables, after the proper implementation of the Data Cube Research Object concept.

3 Application Programming Interface

ADAM exposes standardised Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) services for data discovery, data visualization, access and data processing, to facilitate the integration and exploitation of dataset and product resources within user's stacks.

According to the metadata model [D4.1], a Data Cube provides a series of **functions** to discover, access, visualise and process the **datasets**, namely the aggregation of **products** with common properties into a multi-dimensional digital object with its spatial and temporal dimensions.

The complete list of FAIR Data Cubes can be found in [D4.4]: as example of the Data Cube resources requested by RELIANCE user communities, the **CAMS European air quality forecasts Data Cube** will provide access to hourly products organized in 13 datasets (i.e., different environmental variables, such as ammonia, carbon_monoxide, ...) over Europe from July 2018 to 2021.

An OpenSearch catalogue service (**OpenSearch**) is exposed to discover all data cubes within the platform through the various data facilities. The connection to INSPIRE compliant catalogues is also supported.

The Web Coverage Service (**WCS**) is the core part of the DAS module. WCS can be queried directly via REST calls.

3.1 Data discovery service - OpenSearch

The discovery service exposes the **OpenSearch Geo and Time Extensions** interface to explore the Data Cube resource in each of its own dimensions (space, time, ...). The metadata model adopted by the OpenSearch service is describe in [D4.1]: the description of the service API, including examples are described in the next sections of the document. The pagination mechanism is used to handle the navigation through results.

The service description, including supported operations, can be obtained through the describe operation

- <https://reliance-das.adamplatform.eu/opensearch/describe.xml>

The OpenSearch supports a 2 steps discovery service.

3.1.1 Discovery Level 1: datasets discovery

The generic syntax for the dataset's operation is

```
http://mwcs-test.meeo.datacenter/opensearch/datasets?datasetId={datasetId}&startDate={date:
YYYY-MM-DD | YYYY-MM-DDTHH:MM:SSZ}&endDate={date: YYYY-MM-DD | YYYY-MM-
DDTHH:MM:SSZ}&startIndex={num}&maxRecords={num}
```

where:

- *datasetId* is the identifier of the Data Cube
- *startDate* / *endDate* refer to the time range of the products indexed in the Data Cube
- *startIndex* is the parameter used by the pagination mechanism to flow through the Data Cube resources
- *maxRecords* is the parameter to set the number of resources to be listed in a page

The result of this operation provides the list available datasets, each with the metadata description as defined in [D4.1]. Using the pagination options, it is possible to navigate through the complete list of datasets.

Sample requests

- To get the list of all available datasets: [/datasets](#)

The operation returns the total number of datasets available (i.e., *totalResults*) as well as the paginated list of datasets (i.e., *datasetId*) with the metadata description.


```

JSON  Dati non elaborati  Header
Salva Copia Comprimi tutto Espandi tutto (lento) Filtra JSON
type: "FeatureCollection"
▼ properties:
  id: "https://reliance-das.adamplatform.eu/opensearch/datasets?"
  query:
    request: [...]
    itemsPerPage: "10"
    startIndex: "0"
    totalResults: 56
  links:
    0:
      first: "https://reliance-das.adamplatform.eu/opensearch/datasets?startIndex=0"
    1: [...]
    2: [...]
    3:
      description: "https://reliance-das.adamplatform.eu/opensearch/describe"
  features:
    0: [...]
    1:
      datasetId: "MODh20chL_4km"
      creationDate: "2008-01-01T00:40:01Z"
      dataType: "Float32"
      epsg: "4326"
      keywords: []
      license: []
      maxDate: "2020-12-01T00:00:00Z"
      maxValue: []
      minDate: "2008-01-01T00:40:01Z"
      minValue: []
      noDataValue: "-32767"
      numberOfRecords: 15
  
```

Figure 4 Result example of OpenSearch request to list all available datasets in ADAM

- To get the dataset details: [/datasets?datasetId=MODh20chIMO_4km](#)

The operation returns the metadata description of the selected dataset (i.e., *MODh20chIMO_4km*)

```

JSON  Dati non elaborati  Header
Salva Copia Comprimi tutto Espandi tutto Filtra JSON
type: "FeatureCollection"
properties:
  id: "https://reliance-das.adamplatform.eu/opensearch/datasets?datasetId=M00h20chl_4km&startIndex=0"
  query:
    request:
      0:
        datasetId: "M00h20chl_4km"
        itemsPerPage: "1"
        startIndex: "0"
        totalResults: 1
    links:
      0:
        first: "https://reliance-das.adamplatform.eu/opensearch/datasets?datasetId=M00h20chl_4km&maxRecords=10&startIndex=0"
      1: {}
      2:
        description: "https://reliance-das.adamplatform.eu/opensearch/describe"
features:
  0:
    datasetId: "M00h20chl_4km"
    createDate: "2008-01-01T00:40:01Z"
    dataType: "Float32"
    epsg: "4326"
    keywords: []
    license: {}
    maxDate: "2020-12-01T00:00:00Z"
    maxValue:
      0: 20
      minDate: "2008-01-01T00:40:01Z"
      minValue:
        0: 0.005931331730664
    
```

Figure 5 Result example of OpenSearch request to retrieve details of a datasets in ADAM

3.1.2 Discovery Level 2: discovery of products

The generic query syntax for the search operation is

`http://<service endpoint>/opensearch/search?datasetId={datasetId}&startDate={date: YYYY-MM-DD | YYYY-MM-DDTHH:MM:SSZ}&endDate={date: YYYY-MM-DD | YYYY-MM-DDTHH:MM:SSZ}&geometry={geojson}&startIndex={num}&maxRecords={num}`

where:

- *datasetId* is the identifier of the Data Cube
- *startDate* / *endDate* refer to the time range of the products indexed in the Data Cube
- *geometry* refer to the area of interest of the products indexed in the Data Cube
- *startIndex* is the parameter used by the pagination mechanism to flow through the Data Cube resources
- *maxRecords* is the parameter to set the number of resources to be listed in a page

The result of this operation provides the list available products, each with the metadata description as defined in [D4.1]. Using the pagination options, it is possible to navigate through the complete list of products.

Sample requests

- To get the list of all products: [/search](#)

The operation returns the total number of products available (i.e., *totalResults*) as well as the paginated list of each product (i.e., *productId*) with metadata description.

JSON	Dati non elaborati	Header
Salva	Copia	Comprimi tutto
Espandi tutto		▼ Filtra JSON
type:	"FeatureCollection"	
▼ properties:		
▼ id:	"https://reliance-das.adamplatform.eu/opensearch/search?"	
▼ query:		
▼ request:		
0:	{}	
itemsPerPage:	"10"	
Index:	"0"	
totalResults:	719430	
▼ links:		
0:		
▼ first:	"https://reliance-das.adamplatform.eu/opensearch/search?maxRecords=10&startIndex=0"	
1:	[-]	
2:		
▼ last:	"https://reliance-das.adamplatform.eu/opensearch/search?maxRecords=10&startIndex=719429"	
3:		
▼ description:	"https://reliance-das.adamplatform.eu/opensearch/describe"	
▼ features:		
▼ 0:		
▼ _id:		
\$oid:	"60c33cd76dfeb0806c332e5"	
datasetId:	"SRTH_XSAR"	
productDate:	"2001-01-01T00:00:00Z"	
productId:	"SRTH_XSAR_20010101_E010N20_XSAR_DEM.tif"	
▼ geometry:	[-]	
insertDate:	"2021-06-11T10:37:11Z"	
▶ productPath:	"/SRTH/2001/01/01/SRTH_XS_01_E010N20_XSAR_DEM.tif"	
source:	"nfs://192.168.1.156:/nanfs_01_vol_02/reliance"	
status:	"Online"	
▼ 1:		

Figure 6 Result example of OpenSearch request to retrieve the list of all products in ADAM

- To get the list of all available products for a specific dataset:
/search?datasetId=MODh20chlMO_4km

The operation returns the total number of products available (i.e., *totalResults*) per the selected dataset (i.e., *MODh20chlMO_4km*) as well as the paginated list of each product (i.e., *productId*) with metadata description.

JSON	Dati non elaborati	Header
Salva	Copia	Comprimi tutto
Espandi tutto		▼ Filtra JSON
type:	"FeatureCollection"	
▼ properties:		
▼ id:	"https://reliance-das.adamplatform.eu/opensearch/search?datasetId=MODh20chl_4km&startIndex=0"	
▼ query:		
▼ request:		
0:		
datasetId:	"MODh20chl_4km"	
itemsPerPage:	"10"	
Index:	"0"	
totalResults:	13	
▼ links:		
0:		
▼ first:	"https://reliance-das.adamplatform.eu/opensearch/search?datasetId=MODh20chl_4km&maxRecords=10&startIndex=0"	
1:		
▼ next:	"https://reliance-das.adamplatform.eu/opensearch/search?datasetId=MODh20chl_4km&maxRecords=10&startIndex=10"	
2:		
▼ last:	"https://reliance-das.adamplatform.eu/opensearch/search?datasetId=MODh20chl_4km&maxRecords=10&startIndex=12"	
3:		
▼ description:	"https://reliance-das.adamplatform.eu/opensearch/describe"	
▼ features:		
▼ 0:		
▼ _id:		
\$oid:	"60a27b05c4f40e6c61f16c68"	
datasetId:	"MODh20chl_4km"	
productDate:	"2008-01-01T00:40:01Z"	
▶ productId:	"NETCDF1\mnt/NetApp/nan_hior_a_4km.nc\chlora"	
band:	1	
▼ bandDescription:	"mass_concentration_chlorophyll_concentration_in_sea_water"	
▼ geometry:		
▼ geometries:		

Figure 7 Result example of OpenSearch request to retrieve all products of a datasets in ADAM

- To get the list of available products for a specific dataset over and area of interest and time of interest: /search?datasetId=MODh20chlMO_4km&startDate=2007-07-01&endDate=2007-07-

[31&startIndex=0&maxRecords=3&geometry={"type":"Polygon","coordinates":\[\[\[-60,-40\],\[60,-40\],\[60,40\],\[-60,40\],\[-60,-40\]\]\]}](#)

The operation returns the total number of products available (i.e., *totalResults*) per the selected dataset (i.e., *MODh20chl_4km*) over the time of interest and area of interest, as well as the paginated list of each product (i.e., *productId*) with metadata description.

3.2 Data access service - WCS

The data access service exposes the **Web Coverage Service (WCS)** interface to access the Data Cube resources. The description of the service API, including examples are described in the next sections of the document.

The WCS supports the following operations:

3.2.1 GetCapabilities

This operation allows at retrieving the list of available collections

<https://reliance-das.adamplatform.eu/wcs?service=WCS&Request=GetCapabilities>

This operation is equivalent to the */datasets* request, with a limited metadata schema with respect to OpenSearch service.

This XML file does not appear to have any style information associated with it. The document tree is shown below.

```

<wcs:Capabilities xmlns:wcs="http://www.opengis.net/wcs/2.0" xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance"
xmlns:crs="http://www.opengis.net/wcs/service-extension/ocrs/1.0" xmlns:ows="http://www.opengis.net/ows/2.0" xmlns:gml="http://www.opengis.net/gml/3.2"
xmlns:xlink="http://www.w3.org/1999/xlink" xsi:schemaLocation="http://www.opengis.net/wcs/2.0 http://schemas.opengis.net/wcs/2.0/wcsAll.xsd"
version="2.0.1">
  <ows:ServiceIdentification xmlns="http://www.opengis.net/ows/2.0">
    <ows:Title>MEOO WCS Server - MWCS (Ver. 2.1-29)</ows:Title>
    <ows:Abstract>The WCS Server implementation to access datacubes and images on filesystem</ows:Abstract>
    <ows:ServiceType>OGC WCS</ows:ServiceType>
    <ows:ServiceTypeVersion>2.0.1</ows:ServiceTypeVersion>
    <ows:Profile>http://www.opengis.net/spec/WCS_coverage-encoding_jpeg2000/1.0</ows:Profile>
    <ows:Profile>http://www.opengis.net/spec/WCS_protocol-binding_get-rest/1.0/conf/get-rest</ows:Profile>
    <ows:Profile>http://www.opengis.net/spec/GMLCOV/1.0/conf/gml-coverage</ows:Profile>
    <ows:Profile>http://www.opengis.net/spec/WCS_service-extension_processing/2.0/conf/processing</ows:Profile>
    <ows:Profile>http://www.opengis.net/spec/WCS_protocol-binding_post-xml/1.0</ows:Profile>
    <ows:Profile>http://www.opengis.net/spec/WCS_protocol-binding_soap/1.0</ows:Profile>
    <ows:Profile>http://www.opengis.net/spec/WCS_coverage-encoding_netcdf/1.0</ows:Profile>
    <ows:Profile>http://www.opengis.net/spec/GMLJP2/2.0</ows:Profile>
    <ows:Profile>http://www.opengis.net/spec/WCS_protocol-binding_get-kvp/1.0/conf/get-kvp</ows:Profile>
    <ows:Profile>http://www.opengis.net/spec/WCS_service-extension_range-subsetting/1.0/conf/</ows:Profile>
    <ows:Profile>http://www.opengis.net/spec/WCS_service-extension_scaling/1.0/conf/scaling</ows:Profile>
    <ows:Profile>http://www.opengis.net/spec/WCS_service-extension_interpolation/1.0/conf/interpolation</ows:Profile>
    <ows:Profile>http://www.opengis.net/spec/WCS_coverage-encoding_geotiff/1.0</ows:Profile>
  </ows:ServiceIdentification>
  <ows:ServiceProvider xmlns="http://www.opengis.net/ows/2.0">
    <ows:ProviderName>MEOO S.r.l.</ows:ProviderName>
    <ows:ProviderSite xlink:href="http://www.meo.it/">
  <ows:ServiceContact>
    <ows:IndividualName>MEOO Help Desk</ows:IndividualName>
    <ows:ContactInfo>
      <ows:Address>
        <ows:City>Ferrara</ows:City>
        <ows:PostalCode>I-44123</ows:PostalCode>
        <ows:Country>Italy</ows:Country>
        <ows:ElectronicMailAddress>helpdesk@meoo.it</ows:ElectronicMailAddress>
      </ows:Address>
    </ows:ContactInfo>
    <ows:Role>Service Provider</ows:Role>
  </ows:ServiceContact>

```

Figure 8 Result example of WCS request to retrieve list of datasets (collections) in ADAM

3.2.2 DescribeCoverage

This operation returns the WCS metadata schema for a specific collection

<https://test.adamplatform.eu/wcs?service=WCS&Request=DescribeCoverage&version=2.0.0&coverageId=<CoverageID>>

This operation is equivalent to the */datasets&datasetId={}* request, with a limited metadata schema with respect to OpenSearch service.

The term CoverageId correspond to datasetId.

Sample request

https://reliance-das.adamplatform.eu/wcs?service=WCS&Request=DescribeCoverage&version=2.0.0&coverageID=M0Dh20chlMO_4km

This XML file does not appear to have any style information associated with it. The document tree is shown below.

```

<wcs:CoverageDescriptions xmlns:wcs="http://www.opengis.net/wcs/2.0" xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance"
xmlns:crs="http://www.opengis.net/wcs/service-extension/ocrs/1.0" xmlns:ows="http://www.opengis.net/ows/2.0" xmlns:gml="http://www.opengis.net/gml/3.2"
xmlns:xlink="http://www.w3.org/1999/xlink" xsi:schemaLocation="http://www.opengis.net/wcs/2.0 http://schemas.opengis.net/wcs/2.0/wcsAll.xsd">
  <wcs:CoverageDescription xmlns="http://www.opengis.net/gml/3.2" xmlns:gmlcov="http://www.opengis.net/gmlcov/1.0"
xmlns:swe="http://www.opengis.net/swe/2.0" gml:id="MODh20chl_4km">
    <boundedBy>
      <Envelope srsName="http://www.opengis.net/def/crs-compound?
l=http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSSG/0/4326&2=http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/OGC/0/Temporal?epoch="1970-01-01T00:00:00"&uom="s";"
axisLabels="Lat Long t" uomLabels="degree degree s" srsDimension="3">
        <lowerCorner>0.000000 0.000000 1199148001</lowerCorner>
        <upperCorner>0.000000 0.000000 1606780800</upperCorner>
      </Envelope>
    </boundedBy>
    <domainSet>
      <gmlrgrid:ReferenceableGridByVectors xmlns:gmlrgrid="http://www.opengis.net/gml/3.3/rgrid" dimension="3" gml:id="MODh20chl_4km-grid"
xsi:schemaLocation="http://www.opengis.net/gml/3.3/rgrid http://schemas.opengis.net/gml/3.3/referenceableGrid.xsd">
        <limits>
          <GridEnvelope>
            <low>0 0 0</low>
            <high>2147483647 2147483647 14</high>
          </GridEnvelope>
        </limits>
        <axisLabels>Long Lat t</axisLabels>
        <gmlrgrid:origin>
          <Point gml:id="MODh20chl_4km-origin" srsName="http://www.opengis.net/def/crs-compound?
l=http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSSG/0/4326&2=http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/OGC/0/Temporal?epoch="1970-01-01T00:00:00"&uom="s""
axisLabels="Lat Long t" uomLabels="degree degree s" srsDimension="3">
            <pos>0.000000 0.000000 1199148001</pos>
          </Point>
        </gmlrgrid:origin>
        <gmlrgrid:generalGridAxis>
          <gmlrgrid:GeneralGridAxis>
            <gmlrgrid:offsetVector srsName="http://www.opengis.net/def/crs-compound?
l=http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSSG/0/4326&2=http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/OGC/0/Temporal?epoch="1970-01-01T00:00:00"&uom="s""
axisLabels="Lat Long t" uomLabels="degree degree s" srsDimension="3">0 0.000000 0</gmlrgrid:offsetVector>
            <gmlrgrid:coefficients/>
            <gmlrgrid:gridAxesSpanned>Long</gmlrgrid:gridAxesSpanned>
            <gmlrgrid:sequenceRule axisOrder="+1">Linear</gmlrgrid:sequenceRule>
          </gmlrgrid:GeneralGridAxis>
        </gmlrgrid:generalGridAxis>
      </gmlrgrid:ReferenceableGridByVectors>
    </domainSet>
  </wcs:CoverageDescription>
</wcs:CoverageDescriptions>

```

Figure 9 Result example of WCS request to retrieve details of a dataset (collection) in ADAM

3.2.3 GetCoverage

This operation allows at accessing the products from a dataset. The generic query syntax for the search operation is:

[https://test.adamplatform.eu/wcs?service=WCS&Request=GetCoverage&version=2.0.0&coverageID=<CoverageID>&subset=\[Long\]\[N\]\(min,max\)&subset=\[Lat\]\[E\]\(min,max\)&subset=t\(minDate,maxDate\)&format=<####>&colortable=<ID>&scale=<nn>&size=<output raster size>](https://test.adamplatform.eu/wcs?service=WCS&Request=GetCoverage&version=2.0.0&coverageID=<CoverageID>&subset=[Long][N](min,max)&subset=[Lat][E](min,max)&subset=t(minDate,maxDate)&format=<####>&colortable=<ID>&scale=<nn>&size=<output raster size>)

Where:

- Spatial subsettings values depend on the dataset (see DescribeCoverage output axisLabels).
 - If <axisLabels>Long Lat t</axisLabels> then latitude and longitude values in degrees must be provided
 - If <axisLabels>N E t</axisLabels> then North and East values in meters shall be provided
 - If a 3D collection is provided, subset=h() subsets the vertical dimension
- Time subsetting, dates / times can be provided in ansi or unix time (see examples below)
- format=<##>, where ## = image/tiff, image/png, image/jp2, image/envi, image/gif, text/plain, text/csv, application/xml, application/gml+xml, application/tar, application/json
- colortable=<ID>, ID = https://www.ncl.ucar.edu/Document/Graphics/color_table_gallery.shtml
- colorrange=<min,max>, to apply the colortable between the min/max values
- scale=<nn>, nn is resampling factor (1 native resolution, 0.1 resolution degraded to 10%)
- size=<x,y>, to define the output raster size

Sample requests

MODIS Chlorophyll global on January 1st 2008 in PNG format

[http://reliance-das.adamplatform.eu/wcs?service=WCS&Request=GetCoverage&version=2.0.0&coverageID=MODh20chlMO_4km&subset=unix\(2008-02-01T00:00:00Z\)&format=image/png](http://reliance-das.adamplatform.eu/wcs?service=WCS&Request=GetCoverage&version=2.0.0&coverageID=MODh20chlMO_4km&subset=unix(2008-02-01T00:00:00Z)&format=image/png)

Same as above, but time provided in ANSI format

[http://reliance-das.adamplatform.eu/wcs?service=WCS&Request=GetCoverage&version=2.0.0&coverageID=MODh20chlMO_4km&subset=t\(1201824000\)&format=image/png](http://reliance-das.adamplatform.eu/wcs?service=WCS&Request=GetCoverage&version=2.0.0&coverageID=MODh20chlMO_4km&subset=t(1201824000)&format=image/png)

Figure 10 Result example of WCS request to retrieve a product from a dataset in ADAM

Same as above, but with the MPL_winterInv colortable:

[https://reliance-das.adamplatform.eu/wcs?service=WCS&Request=GetCoverage&version=2.0.0&coverageID=MODh20chlMO_4km&subset=unix\(2008-02-01T00:00:00Z\)&format=image/png&colortable=MPL_winterInv](https://reliance-das.adamplatform.eu/wcs?service=WCS&Request=GetCoverage&version=2.0.0&coverageID=MODh20chlMO_4km&subset=unix(2008-02-01T00:00:00Z)&format=image/png&colortable=MPL_winterInv)

Figure 11 Result example of WCS request to retrieve a product from a dataset in ADAM with MPL_winterInv colortable

4 References

[D4.1] Corcho O., Gonzalez E., Garijo D., Foglini F., Trasatti E., Fouilloux A., Mantovani S., Gonçalves P. “D4.1 Data Cube Metadata Model”, RELIANCE project deliverable. May 10th 2021.

[D4.4] Mantovani S. “D4.4 FAIR Data Cubes - Release I”, RELIANCE project deliverable. July 2021.